

Supplementary Data

Table 1a Adverse events following single vaccination

Vaccine	Number	Male	Female	Time to onset <=7 days	Time to onset >7 days
ChAdOx1	7	3	4	3	4
mRNA1273	4	2	2	4	0
BNT1262b	15	10	5	14	1

Table 1b Adverse events following second vaccination

Vaccine	Number	Male	Female	Time to onset <=7 days	Time to onset >7 days	Undefined
ChAdOx1	1	0	1	0	0	1
mRNA1273	30	29	1	29	1	
BNT1262b	61	56	5	57	4	

Table 1c Adverse events following third vaccination

Vaccine	Number	Male	Female	Time to onset <=7 days	Time to onset >7 days
ChAdOx1	0	0	0	0	0
mRNA1273	22	2 (%)	20 (%)	22	0
BNT1262b	1	0	1	1	0

Table 1d Adverse events per dose per vaccine

Vaccine	1st Dose	2nd Dose	3rd Dose
ChAdOx1	7	1	0
mRNA1273	4	30	22
BNT1262b	15	61	1

Table 2a: Total Adverse events according to age group

Age Band	Total adverse events
11-20	34
21-30	26
31-40	20
41-50	13
51-60	11
61-70	13
71-80	3
81-90	1
Undefined	24

Table 2b Deaths according to age band and sex

Age Band	Deaths	
	Male	Female
11-20	0	0
21-30	2	1
31-40	2	1
41-50	2	0
51-60	0	0
61-70	2	1
71-80	0	0
81-90	0	0

Table 3a Adverse events according to age group, sex and myocardial involvement

Age Band	Myocarditis		Other	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
11-20	31	2	1	0
21-30	20	5	0	1
31-40	10	7	1	2
41-50	5	5	1	2
51-60	4	5	0	2
61-70	1	5	5	2
71-80	1	0	0	2
81-90	0	0	0	1
Undefined	23	0	1	0

Table 3b Deaths according to age group and myocardial involvement

Age Band	Myocarditis	Other
11-20	0	0
21-30	3	0
31-40	4	1
41-50	2	0
51-60	1	0
61-70	1	2
71-80	0	0
81-90	0	0

Table 4a Myocarditis with eosinophil

Male	Female	Reference(s)
0	1	Ameratunga et al 2022
3	1	Cho et al 2023a
2	1	Frustaci et al 2022
1	0	Janga et al (2023)
1	0	Kimura et al (2022)
1	0	Minato et al (2024)
1	1	Verma et al (2021)

Table 4b: Other adverse events with Eosinophil

Condition	Number		Reference(s)
	M	F	
DRESS/DIHS	1	1	O,Connor et al (2022), Schroeder et al (2022)
pneumonia	2	3	e Silva et al (2022); May et al (2022); Miqdadi et al (2021); Piqueras et al (2022)
cellulitis	2	1	Cinotti et al (2022); De Montjoye et al (2021); Ikedobi et al (2022)
granulomatosis with polyangiitis	0	2	Chan-chung et al (2021); Ibrahim et al (2022)
enteritis	1	0	Doman et al (2023)
pustular folliculitis	0	1	Rikitake et al (2022)
Multiple conditions	0	1	Morikawa et al (2022)

Table 5a Myocarditis reported without Eosinophils

Male	Female	Reference(s)
1	0	Albert et al (2021)
1	0	Alizadeh et al (2022)
2	0	Amodio et al (2023)
2	20	Buergin et al (2023)
3	1	Cho et al (2023)
1	0	Cimaglia et al (2022)
1	0	D'Angelo et al (2021)
14	1	Dionne et al (2021)
1	0	Garcia et al (2021)
3	1	Kim et al (2021)
8	0	Larson et al (2021)
0	1	Lim et al (2021)
7	0	Marshall et al (2021)
1	0	McClellan et al (2021)
1	0	Minocha et al (2021)
23	0	Montgomery et al (2021)
6	0	Mouch et al (2021)
1	0	Muthukumar et al (2021)
3	1	Parmar et al (2022)
7	0	Rosner et al (2021)

Table 5b Other conditions with no eosinophils

Male	Female	Reference(s)
0	1	Ando et al (2022)
2	2	Schneider et al (2021)
1	0	Gill et al (2022b)

Table 6 Summary of adverse events by age and sex

Age Range	Myocarditis				Other Conditions			
	Non Eosinophilic		Eosinophilic		Non Eosinophilic		Eosinophilic	
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
11-20	31	2	0	0	0	0	1	0
21-30	19	5	1	0	0	1	0	0
31-40	8	5	2	2	0	0	1	2
41-50	2	4	3	1	0	0	1	2
51-60	3	4	1	1	0	1	0	1
61-70	0	5	1	0	2	1	3	1
71-80	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2
81-90	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Undefined	23	0	0	0	1	0	0	0

Table 7: Summary of references

Age (M/F)	Number of doses (Vaccine)	Period before adverse event (days)	Co-morbidities/ Past Medical History/Findings/treatment	Diagnosis/Outcome	Reference
24 (M)	2 (mRNA1273)	4	Nil	myocarditis	Albert et al (2021)
29 (M)	1 (ChAdOx1)	3	Nil	myocarditis	Alizadeh et al (2022)
57 (F)	1 (BNT162b2)	1	Nil	Fulminant necrotising myocarditis (deceased)	Ameratunga et al (2022)
15 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	4	Undiagnosed CoViD-19 infection	Myocarditis	Amodio et al (2023)
		270	Relapse	Myocarditis	
16 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	1	SARS-CoV-2 infection 4 months post vaccination	myocarditis	
		365	Relapse	myocarditis	
55 (F)	3 (BNT162b2)	1	Marfan, aortic dissections 2 nd vaccination 8 months prior	Acute onset of asthma	Ando et al (2022)
96 (F)	1 (mRNA1273)	24	Nil	Myocardial Infarction	Boivin and Martin(2021)
49 (M)	3 (mRNA1273)	3	Asymptomatic		Buergin et al (2023)
36 (F)	3 (mRNA1273)	3	Asymptomatic		
30 (F)	3 (mRNA1273)	3	Dyspnoea, pyrexia		
20 (F)	3 (mRNA1273)	3	Asymptomatic		
46 (F)	3 (mRNA1273)	3	Chest Pain		
49 (F)	3 (mRNA1273)	3	Asymptomatic		
57 (F)	3 (mRNA1273)	3	Asymptomatic		
62 (F)	3 (mRNA1273)	3	Asymptomatic		
37 (F)	3 (mRNA1273)	3	Asymptomatic		
46 (F)	3 (mRNA1273)	3	Asymptomatic		
64 (F)	3 (mRNA1273)	3	Asymptomatic		
26 (F)	3 (mRNA1273)	3	Asymptomatic		
32 (F)	3 (mRNA1273)	3	Pyrexia		

Age (M/F)	Number of doses (Vaccine)	Period before adverse event (days)	Co-morbidities/ Past Medical History/Findings/treatment	Diagnosis/Outcome	Reference
62 (F)	3 (mRNA1273)	3	Asymptomatic	Myocarditis diagnosed by raised hs-cTnT levels at day 3	
61 (F)	3 (mRNA1273)	3	Asymptomatic		
37 (F)	3 (mRNA1273)	3	Pyrexia		
26 (F)	3 (mRNA1273)	3	Pyrexia		
22 (F)	3 (mRNA1273)	3	Asymptomatic		
54 (F)	3 (mRNA1273)	3	Pyrexia		
53 (F)	3 (mRNA1273)	3	Asymptomatic		
54 (M)	3 (mRNA1273)	3	Pyrexia		
43 (F)	3 (mRNA1273)	3	Chest pain, pyrexia		
62 (F)	2 (ChAdOx1)	few days	Mild asthma	Diagnosed with Eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis	Chan-chung et al (2021)
36 (F)	1 (mRNA1273)	2	Neutrophil, eosinophil, and histiocyte infiltration in the myocardium suggesting acute myocarditis.	Sudden Cardiac Death	Cho et al (2023)
33 (M)	2 (mRNA1273)	1	Multiple focal infiltrations of acute inflammatory cells and chronic inflammatory cells in the myocardium.	Sudden Cardiac Death	
33 (M)	2 (mRNA1273)	3	Various inflammatory cells such as neutrophils, eosinophils, lymphocytes, macrophages, and cardiomyocyte necrosis in the myocardial interstitium and epicardium suggested myocarditis.	Sudden Cardiac Death .	
22 (M)	1 (BNT162b2)	6	Diffuse inflammatory infiltration, with neutrophil and histiocyte predominance in both atria and near AV node and SA node. Free of inflammatory infiltrates in ventricular myocardium.	Sudden Cardiac Death	
30 (F)	1 (BNT162b2)	3	Diffuse inflammatory cell infiltration, myocardial fiber disarray, interstitial fibrosis, and localized necrosis of myocyte.	Sudden Cardiac Death	

Age (M/F)	Number of doses (Vaccine)	Period before adverse event (days)	Co-morbidities/ Past Medical History/Findings/treatment	Diagnosis/Outcome	Reference
12-18 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	1-6 days (median 3)		Myocarditis	
12-18 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	1-6 days (median 3)		Myocarditis	
12-18 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	1-6 days (median 3)		Myocarditis	
12-18 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	1-6 days (median 3)		Myocarditis	
12-18 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	1-6 days (median 3)		Myocarditis	
12-18 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	1-6 days (median 3)		Myocarditis	
12-18 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	1-6 days (median 3)		Myocarditis	
61 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	0.25	Type 2 DM hyperuricaemia	Eosinophilic enteritis	Doman et al (2023)
Age Unknown (F)	2 (BNT162b2)	5	coronary heart disease CABG, cardiac insufficiency, arterial hypertension, dementia and hyperthyroidism	CoD pulmonary artery embolism unrelated to vaccination	Edler et al (2021)
Age Unknown (M)	1 (BNT162b2)	7	chronic renal failure, anemia, atrial fibrillation, pulmonary artery embolism, arterial hypertension, peripheral artery disease, right thalamic infarction with left hemiparesis, recurrent tonic-clonic seizures, gait disorder with polyneuropathy, rheumatoid arthritis and prostate carcinoma with prostatectomy	CoD CoViD19 pneumonia unrelated to vaccination	
Age Unknown (M)	unclear(BNT162b2)	2	apoplexy and myocardial infarction as well as arterial hypertension and type II diabetes mellitus	CoD natural causes unrelated to vaccine	
38 (F)	Unclear (unknown)	14	Ex smoker	Eosinophilic pneumonia	e Silva et al (2022)
47 (F)	Unknown (unknown)	28	Unresolved pneumonia with eosinophilia 2009	Eosinophilic pneumonia	

Age (M/F)	Number of doses (Vaccine)	Period before adverse event (days)	Co-morbidities/ Past Medical History/Findings/treatment	Diagnosis/Outcome	Reference
39 (F)	2 (BNT162b2)	14		Eosinophilic myocarditis	Frustaci et al (2022)
78 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	14		Eosinophilic myocarditis	
52 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	14		Eosinophilic myocarditis	
39 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	0.25	asthma, autoimmune hypothyroidism, chronic atrophic gastritis, an isolated episode of atrial fibrillation, and recurrent spontaneous pneumothorax	myocarditis	Garcia et al (2021)
Middle age (M)	1 (BNT162b2)	1	EGPA associated with polyneuropathy (2012) in remission (from 2015)	recrudescence of underlying asymptomatic polyneuropathy	Gill et al (2022b)
79 (F)	2 (BNT162b2)	(unclear)	Asthma GORD Sleep apnoea	eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis	Ibrahim et al (2022)
12 (M)	1 (BNT162b2)	1	asthma, urticaria, peanut allergy	Vaccine induced Wells syndrome (Eosinophilic cellulitis)	Ikedioji et al (2022)
24 (M)	2 (mRNA1273)	84	Allergic rhinitis exposed to CoViD-19 6 months prior	Delayed Eosinophilic Myocarditis	Janga et al (2023)
36 (M)	2 (mRNA1273)	3	No serology performed All patients discharged from hospital 2 to 4 days after admission	myocarditis	Kim et al (2021)
70 (F)	2 (mRNA1273)	1		myocarditis	
23 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	5		myocarditis	
24 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	2		myocarditis	
69 (M)	1 (BNT162b2)	7	Nil	Fulminant eosinophilic myocarditis	Kimura et al (2022)
XXX 31 (M)	1 (mRNA1273)	2	Started allopurinol 38 days prior to hospitalisation	DRESS/DIHS	

Age (M/F)	Number of doses (Vaccine)	Period before adverse event (days)	Co-morbidities/ Past Medical History/Findings/treatment	Diagnosis/Outcome	Reference	
68 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	3 6	Started carbamazepine 7 weeks before hospitalisation	DRESS/DIHS	Korekwa et al (2022)	
72 (M)	1 (BNT162b2)	3	Type 2 Diabetes, emphysema Started carbamazepine 58 days before hospitalisation	DRESS/DIHS		
22 (M)	2 (mRNA1273)	3	Hemodynamically stable, no clinical heart failure; intermittent chest pain resolved with ibuprofen and steroids	myocarditis	Larson et al (2021)	
31 (M)	2 (mRNA1273)	3	Hemodynamically stable, no clinical heart failure; chest pain resolved with acetaminophen	myocarditis		
22 (M)	2 (mRNA1273)	2	NSVT episodes (N=3); discharged stable	myocarditis		
40 (M)	1 (BNT162b2)	2	Previous SARS-CoV-2 infection Hemodynamically stable; endomyocardial biopsy found no active myocarditis	myocarditis		
56 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	3	Previous SARS-CoV-2 infection Hemodynamically stable	myocarditis		
26 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	3	2 days in intensive care; no inotropes or mechanical circulatory support; discharged stable	myocarditis		
35 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	2	4 days in intensive care; no inotropes or mechanical circulatory support; discharged stable	myocarditis		
21 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	4	2 days in intensive care; no inotropes or mechanical circulatory support; NSVT episode; discharged stable	myocarditis		
38 (F)	1 (BNT162b2)	7	No Past medical history	Fulminant Myocarditis		Lim et al (2021)
16 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	2		myocarditis		Marshall et al (2021)
19 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	3		myocarditis		

Age (M/F)	Number of doses (Vaccine)	Period before adverse event (days)	Co-morbidities/ Past Medical History/Findings/treatment	Diagnosis/Outcome	Reference
20 – 51 (M)	2 (mRNA1273)	0.5 to 4			
20 – 51 (M)	2 (mRNA1273)	0.5 to 4			
20 – 51 (M)	2 (mRNA1273)	0.5 to 4			
20 – 51 (M)	2 (mRNA1273)	0.5 to 4			
20 – 51 (M)	2 (mRNA1273)	0.5 to 4			
20 – 51 (M)	2 (mRNA1273)	0.5 to 4			
20 – 51 (M)	2 (mRNA1273)	0.5 to 4			
20 – 51 (M)	1 (BNT162b2)	0.5 to 4	Confirmed covid infection >2 months prior to vaccination		
20 – 51 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	0.5 to 4			
20 – 51 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	0.5 to 4			
20 – 51 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	0.5 to 4			
20 – 51 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	0.5 to 4			
20 – 51 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	0.5 to 4			
20 – 51 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	0.5 to 4			
20 – 51 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	0.5 to 4			
88 (F)	1 (BNT162b2)	3	Chronic Eosinophilic Pneumonia diagnosed 2002 with Bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL) eosinophils 75%	joint and respiratory symptoms worsening. Laboratory examinations showed increased RF, anti-cyclin citrullinated peptide antibody, and peripheral absolute eosinophil count. synovitis.	Morikawa et al (2022)

Age (M/F)	Number of doses (Vaccine)	Period before adverse event (days)	Co-morbidities/ Past Medical History/Findings/treatment	Diagnosis/Outcome	Reference
24 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	3		myocarditis	Mouch et al (2021)
20 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	1		myocarditis	
29 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	2		myocarditis	
45 (M)	1 (BNT162b2)	16		myocarditis	
16 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	1		myocarditis	
17 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	3		myocarditis	
52 (M)	2 (mRNA1273)	3		myocarditis	Muthukumar et al (2021)
45 (F)	1 (ChAdOx1)	49		Diagnosed with DRESS/DIHS	O'Connor et al (2022)
53 (F)	1 (mRNA1273)	6		myocarditis	Parmar et al (2022)
22 (M)	2 (mRNA1273)	3		myocarditis	
19 (M)	2 (mRNA1273)	4		myocarditis	
22 (M)	2 (mRNA1273)	3		Myocarditis	
37 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	0.2	Nil	Acute eosinophilic pneumonia	Piqueras et al (2022)
38 (F)	2 (BNT162b2)	2	Presented 9 days after development of itchy folliculocentric papules on upper left arm	Diagnose with eosinophilic pustular folliculitis (EPF)	Rikitake et al (2022)
28 (M)	(Ad26COVS10)	5		myocarditis	Rosner et al (2021)
39 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	3		myocarditis	
39 (M)	2 (mRNA1273)	4		myocarditis	

Age (M/F)	Number of doses (Vaccine)	Period before adverse event (days)	Co-morbidities/ Past Medical History/Findings/treatment	Diagnosis/Outcome	Reference
24 (M)	1 (BNT162b2)	7		myocarditis	
19 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	2		myocarditis	
20 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	3		myocarditis	
23 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	3		Myocarditis	
82 (M)	1 (mRNA1273)	1	No evidence of link to vaccine		Schneider et al (2021)
91 (F)	1 (mRNA1273)	1	No evidence of link to vaccine		
32 (F)	1 (ChAdOx1)	12	Highly likely linked to vaccine, anti-PF4 heparin antibody tests: positive, HIPA-Test: positive, PIPA-Test: positive	Massive cerebral haemorrhage	
34 (F)	1 (ChAdOx1)	1	No evidence of link to vaccine		
48 (F)	1 (ChAdOx1)	10	No evidence of link to vaccine		
65 (M)	1 (BNT162b2)	1	Possible link to vaccine Severe coronary sclerosis, massive cardiac hypertrophy, myocardial infarction scars, myocarditis, anaphylaxis diagnostics negative	Myocarditis in the presence of severe pre-existing cardiac changes,	
71 (M)	1(BNT162b2)	1	No evidence of link to vaccine		
57 (F)	2 (ChAdOx1)	6	No evidence of link to vaccine		
63 (M)	1 (ChAdOx1)	14	No evidence of link to vaccine		
61 (M)	1 (ChAdOx1)	1	No evidence of link to vaccine		
71 (M)	Unknown (ChAdOx1)	10	No evidence of link to vaccine		

Age (M/F)	Number of doses (Vaccine)	Period before adverse event (days)	Co-morbidities/ Past Medical History/Findings/treatment	Diagnosis/Outcome	Reference
38 (F)	1 (ChAdOx1)	8	Unlikely link to vaccine		
72 (F)	1 (BNT162b2)	12	No evidence of link to vaccine		
65 (F)	1 (ChAdOx1)	10	Very Likely Signs of a bleeding diathesis, cerebral brain hemorrhages, CVT, mild coronary sclerosis, anti-PF4 heparin antibody tests: positive, HIPA-Test: positive, PIPA-Test: positive	CVT and cerebral haemorrhage with hypoxic brain damage	
79 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	6	No evidence of link to vaccine		
57 (m)	Unknown (ChAdOx1)	2	No evidence of link to vaccine		
72 (F)	2 (BNT162b2)	0	No evidence of link to vaccine		
69 (M)	(Ad26COVS1)	9	Possible link to vaccine CVT, severe coronary sclerosis with coronary thrombosis, massive cardiac hypertrophy, fresh myocardial infarction, anti-PF4 heparin antibody tests: positive, HIPA-Test: positive, PIPA-Test: positive	Coronary thrombosis with fresh myocardial infarction	
47 (M)	2 (BNT162b2)	5	ulcerative rectocolitis, allergic asthma, angioedema after aspirin no other known allergies medication: inhalation therapy for asthma and mesalazine for ulcerative colitis.	DIHS/DRESS	Schroeder et al (2022)
68 (F)	1 (mRNA1273)	1	Hypertension Coronary Artery Disease BMI 46.6	Myocardial Infarction	Sung et al (2021)

Age (M/F)	Number of doses (Vaccine)	Period before adverse event (days)	Co-morbidities/ Past Medical History/Findings/treatment	Diagnosis/Outcome	Reference
42 (M)	1 (mRNA1273)	0.5	FHx Coronary artery disease BMI 42.8	Myocardial Infarction	
45 (F)	1 (BNT1262b)	10	Eosinophils, T cells, macrophages, B cells, plasma cells found on endomyocardial biopsy	Fulminant Myocarditis	Verma et al (2021)
42 (M)	2 (mRNA1273)	14	inflammatory infiltrate admixed with macro- phages, T-cells, eosinophils, and B cells found on post mortem	Fulminant Myocarditis	